

**Letter to the editor: WORLD ASSOCIATION OF
MEDICAL EDITORS (WAME) aims and Policies (A Letter
from the WAME Board)**

Peush Sahni from India (WAME President)

E-mail: peush_sahni@hotmail.com

Ana Marusic from Croatia, WAME Past President

Margaret Winker from the USA, WAME Secretary

Farrokh Habibzadeh from Iran, WAME Director

Pritpal S. Tamber, WAME Director

Faith McLellan, WAME Director

Herbert Stegemann, WAME Director

Robert Fletcher, Chair, Editorial Policy Committee

Bruce Squires from Canada , Chair, Membership Committee

Dear Editor,

The recent discussions in relation to policies of individual Journals being in conflict with WAME policy statements caused the WAME Board to re-examine the bylaws and purposes. Based on the discussions that the Board has had over the past few days. We hope, clarifying the purposes for which WAME was started and will continue to strive for, in the following statement.

Board WAME Statement

The Board of Directors of WAME encourages all editors to adhere to WAME Policies. We reemphasize Article II of present Bylaws, the purpose of WAME: "The mission of WAME is to promote the best of scientific medicine in order to improve the health of the public.

(1) Facilitate cooperation and communication among editors of medical journals throughout the world.

(2) Improve editorial standards and promote professionalism in medical editing through education, self-criticism, and self-governance.

(3) Promote research in peer review and medical editing."

Its specific purposes are to: In essence, the purpose of WAME is to aid and encourage, not force, good editorial practices.

We believe that science should transcend political boundaries and editors should provide leadership in furthering the goals of WAME. However, individual editors, not journals, join WAME, and they serve in cooperation.